

THE ROLE OF EASTERN THINKERS IN IMMUNICATING ENLIGHTENMENT TO STUDENTS AND YOUNG PEOPLE

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Today, many systematic works are being carried out in our country for the decent life of our people. The beginning of such effective work dates back to the 9th-12th centuries. This is because we can feel that our ancestors who lived and created in that period, in their works and theories, only looked out for the benefit of people and wanted to elevate them. IX-XII centuries in the history of the peoples of Central Asia were the years of sharp rise in the development of cultural and spiritual life compared to previous periods. During this period, science flourished in Movaraunnakhr, a real foundation was created for many branches and directions of modern science. In particular, the foundation stone of secular sciences such as mathematics, algebra, astronomy, medicine, geology, geodesy, geography, and philosophy were literally laid during this period. Muhammad Musa al-Khorazimi, Ahmad al-Marwazi, Ahmad al-Farghani, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Bakr Muhammad Narshahi, Abu Abdullah al-Khorazimi, Abu Raikhan Beruni, Abu Bakr al-Khorazimi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Mahmud az - We can learn that our ancestors like Zamakshari, Burkhaniddin Marginani spent their whole lives in science while studying their works. For example, when we look at the work of Muhammad ibn al-Khorazimi, his treatise "Al-kitab al-mukhtasar fi hisab al-jabr wa al-muqabala" attracts special attention. The words "al-jabr" and "al-muqabala" in the title of the treatise refer to two basic operations of medieval algebra: "completion" and "opposite".

The word "Algebra" when translated from Latin became "Algebra" and became the name of the new science founded by Khorezimi. Khorezmi's name remained in the form of the term "algorithm" in mathematics. The rules of writing numbers in the decimal system and performing arithmetic operations on them, which have become the most important element of the universal culture today, were introduced thanks to al-Khwarizmi's "Book on Indian Calculation". The great figures of the Islamic world, such as Imam al-Bukhari, Abu Isa at-Tirmizi, Abu Mansur Moturidi, Khwaja Ahmad Yassavi, Bakhovuddin Naqshband, Khwaja Ahrar Vali, who have flourished in our country, during the development and promotion of our holy religion of Islam, have helped people only. We can know that he called for honesty and integrity. The collection of hadiths of Imam al-Bukhari, the founder of hadith science, who lived and created in the years 810-870, called "Al-jame as-sahih", i.e. "Reliable collection", is the most reliable and perfect among the collections of hadiths compiled by other muhaddiths in the Islamic world. Imam al-Bukhari says: "The disaster of

knowledge is to forget it and to waste it by teaching it to people who have no motivation for it." The meaning of this is that a person with knowledge observes the people around him and wants to explain that teaching knowledge to people who do not want to learn and do not get results even if he teaches it is a sign of the waste of knowledge. In this regard, Hazrat Alisher Navoi quotes the following sentence: "A scholar who learns by asking, a tyrant who does not ask." All of the above emphasize that a person should live a decent life, whatever he wants to achieve, all the conditions have been created and his destiny is in his hands.

Many opinions have been expressed about enlightenment. In the eyes of the Sufis, the continuation and derivative of the tariqat is enlightenment. It is a science that surpasses thought and leaves no reason for doubt. Enlightenment is also referred to as "inner knowledge". Because Sufism combined worldly and religious sciences together and called them "apparent sciences". According to them, it is difficult to know God only with external knowledge. However, there is another point of view: although external knowledge is not suitable for understanding the secrets of the Almighty, knowing God must begin with knowing the world. "Enlightenment is sent by truth. This is not my opinion, but divine inspiration," writes Ibn al-Arabi.

The first President I.A. Karimov said the following in his answers to the questions of the reporter of "Fidokor" newspaper:

"Our centuries-old history shows that the role of enlightenment, especially social sciences, in the formation of human worldview is incomparable. Whether it is sociology, history, philosophy, political science, psychology or economics - all of them have a great influence on the intellectual development of a person.

But what is the ideology of the textbooks, program manuals, and books used in the educational processes of higher educational institutions today? Who can guarantee that they have completely abandoned the ideological views left over from the old regime? We have to talk about it again and again. Unfortunately, we have to admit that the development of social sciences in our country lags behind the requirements of the times. We must take measures to immediately eliminate errors and shortcomings in this regard."

Understanding the real truth in the social sphere is several times more difficult than in natural and exact sciences. Because concepts in the social sphere are formed historically. In order to understand them, it is necessary to study the history of the nation and its cultural heritage in depth. A person who thinks that it is possible to understand the problems of this field in Asia based on the study of the history of statehood experienced by European countries is seriously mistaken. For the same reason, the formational theory that Marxists wanted to apply to the historical development of all mankind did not justify itself. Therefore, if we try to solve our problems by creatively interpreting the great heritage created by our ancestors in accordance with the requirements of today, without trying in vain to respond to the urgent problems that arise in a specific time and place on a "universal" scale, we will save ourselves, we would have acted without distracting others.

If science is not impartial, it will not be science, and realistic results will not be achieved. Regardless of what the goal is, science that is not based on objective research is not science. From this point of view, we must finally admit a bitter truth: most of the "researches" conducted in the field of social sciences in the conditions of the former USSR were not real science, but ideology.

Today, we sometimes narrowly interpret the concept of "enlightenment" and think of it as learning science, creating knowledge from various fields. Even in the past, philosophers like Farobi and poets like Yusuf Khos Hajib understood the mind, the knowledge acquired through logical thinking, as the main path leading to happiness.

According to the allegory of our ancestors, spirituality is the divine light reflected in the human heart, the light of the Supreme Truth, and it is necessary for the human heart to be polished in order to be able to reflect it in itself. After all, the rust of selfishness and malice takes over an unpolished heart, and ignorance and darkness begin to prevail in the psyche of such a person. When it is said that "the streets of the soul do not begin", it is probably meant to be lost and lost in the streets of the soul that remain in this darkness.

The process of polishing the human heart is called enlightenment. Enlightenment consists of paths leading to spirituality, and Alisher Navoi describes the "valley of enlightenment" in the epic "Lison ut-Tair" as follows:

"This is such a valley that is crossed by a hundred and a thousand different roads, but not one of them is the same as the other. The opposition between the whole and the part is also present here. Both progress and decline are here. In it you will see a hundred travelers in an unstable way, each of them going a different way. Each of them is proud of the path he is on, each turns the path in his own direction. The way that one likes, the other does not like, each of them sees his own way, but does not consider the other's.

The process of spiritual maturity takes place in different dimensions. One is during the lifetime of an individual, the other is in the historical development of the nation, or on a regional scale, on a global scale, etc. These processes are definitely connected with each other. For example, the formation of the spirituality of an individual depends in many respects on the level of national and universal spiritual development, while the spiritual development of a nation occurs due to changes in the spiritual world of its constituents. It is known that the spiritual development of our nation can be divided into three major periods, each of which is a continuation of the previous one, and differs in its fundamental characteristics.

The first of them - the period of formation of our national spirituality before Islam, which lasted several thousand years, can be compared to the years of human infancy, childhood, and adolescence. A young child does not yet have a well-developed logical thinking, he believes in fairy tales, legends, life seems like a magical fairy tale for a child. The same situation is characteristic of the thinking of most people in the period of the primitive community and the first cities. As if a baby perceives the human race in the scale

of its family members - parents, siblings, the world in the scale of the house in which it lives, primitive man cannot yet imagine either humanity or the nation as a whole, family, clan ', thinks at the level of community, tribe, nation. For a primitive man, humanity is not outside the members of his family, the clan community (as a big family), later, the tribe, the people. In conclusion, it can be said that today's ideological landfills are more powerful than nuclear landfills. The thing that always urges one to be aware of this issue is that if there is military, economic, political pressure, it can be sensed, seen, prevented, but the ideological pressure, its effects and consequences are extremely fast. In such a situation, if a person does not have his own independent opinion, life-national values that have passed the test of time, a worldview formed on a healthy basis and a strong will, he will face various spiritual threats, their sometimes overt and sometimes hidden forms. it is impossible to withstand the effects.

This can be clearly observed in the examples of many events that occur in everyday life, and I think that there is no need to explain for a long time what serious consequences they lead to. The events that took place in the world and in our region over the past years, which we experienced directly, the development of ideological processes repeatedly prove that this conclusion is correct. Today, our young people receive various information and information not only in educational institutions, but also through media such as radio and television, the press, and the Internet. In such a situation, where the global information space is expanding, not only surrounding the minds of our youth, but also giving one-sided education that they should not read it and not see it, surrounding them with an iron wall, without a doubt, also meets the requirements of the times, does not correspond to our noble goals.

Why, we have set ourselves the task of building an open and free democratic society in our country, and we will never turn back from this path.

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